

Effective Utilization of Kanyashree One-Time Grant in West Bengal: Where Problem Arises

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Introduction

The word 'empowerment' conveys a wide range of meanings, explanations, definitions and disciplines with an all-encompassing aspect of psychology and philosophy to the substantially commercialized self-help industry and motivational sciences. (Sutton and Pollock, 2000) Empowerment is greatly needed when there is discrimination of sex, religion, disability, race or ethnicity. (Nussbaum, 1995) Regarding women empowerment, it is believed that if women perceive their conditions, know their rights and learn skills traditionally denied to them, it will empower them easily. (Human Development Report, UNDP 2007-2008)

The CCT (Conditional Cash Transfer) schemes in South Asia in general, and India in particular, have a strong gender focus for improving the opportunities for girls. The CCTs across the continents also had a positive impact on the attitudes towards educating girls. They enhanced the status of women and their decision making ability since the financial benefits are usually transferred to women of the recipient households. (Son, 2008).

Gender equality through promoting women empowerment has remained central to policy discourses in India. Likewise, the Kanyashree Prakalpa is a flagship scheme of the Government of West Bengal to empower adolescent girls through conditional cash transfer (CCT) directly to their bank accounts. The overarching objectives of the scheme are:

- Retention in education for a longer period of time, and complete secondary, higher secondary, higher education, or equivalent in technical, vocational or sports streams, thereby giving them a better footing in both the economic and social spheres.
- Delaying marriage till at least age 18, the legal age of marriage, thereby reducing the risks of early pregnancies, associated risks of maternal and child mortality, and other debilitating health conditions, including those of malnutrition.
- Laying the foundation for the financial inclusion of girls by mandating that its financial benefits are paid into bank accounts where the Kanyashree beneficiary herself is the account holder.

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- Effecting changes in attitudes, perceptions and behavior of adolescent girls, their families and other significant stakeholders in their lives and promoting gender equity through a focused communication strategy. (Assessment of Kanyashree Prakalpa, 2017)

A vital component of this scheme is providing the One-time scholarship of 25,000 rupees to girls enrolled in educational institutes registered in West Bengal on attaining 18 years. Experiences from across the world convincingly illustrate that education has the potential to act as an antidote to child marriage. Early marriage is both a cause and a consequence of girls dropping out of school and once married or pregnant, rarely these girls make it back to education (Brown, 2012). Poor parents usually withdraw girls from school due to economic reasons. Financial incentives in the form of conditional cash transfers to parents to keep their daughter in school as well as delaying their marriage can have significant impact in South Asian societies. (Sekher, 2010) Hence, this study aims to explore the effective utilization of this One-Time grant in the district of South 24 Parganas of West Bengal.

Literature Review

Various studies have been done regarding women empowerment and the role of public services in achieving it. According to Mello and Schmink (2017), women's economic empowerment contributed to their strengthened capacity for adaptive governance in the household due to greater access to resources and more decision-making power about land use. Also, as per Bushra and Wajiha (2015), the content of education, economic opportunity available for women etc. increases their empowerment. A study by Mehaboob and Halder (2019) shows that the interest of girls in pursuing higher education has increased and child marriage rate has decreased due to Kanyashree Prakalpa. Another study done by Ghara and Roy (2017) reveals that the performance of all districts of the state in implementing Kanyashree are not the same. Districts far-away from the state capital Kolkata (like Darjeeling and Siliguri) were better performers as compared to nearby districts of North and South 24 Parganas. The Bangladesh Female Secondary Stipend Programme raised the enrollment of girls in sixth through eighth grade by 8 to 12 percent (Khandker et.al, 2003). A short-term impact evaluation of FSSP in Pakistan found an increase in the enrollment of girls of about 9 percentage points between 2003 to 2005 (Chaudhury and Parajuli, 2008). Another study in Haryana observed that being a CCT beneficiary girl increases the probability of being in school after age 15 by 23 percent (Nanda, et.al, 2014). Mir (2018), in his study, shows that the conditional cash transfer through Kanyashree to the girls aged 13-18 years enhances their social power and self-esteem. Mukherjee and Mukherjee (2020) conducted a study amongst Kanyashree recipients from North 24 Parganas, Kolkata and Burdwan districts. They showed in their study that although most of the Kanyashree beneficiaries used the money for education, cases of early marriage, school dropout and use of one-time grant for marriage and

other non-educational purposes were prevalent amongst them. Another study by Akhter and Deb (2020) shows that Kanyashree Prakalpa, through providing financial assistance to girls, increases decision-making power of girls within the family and also increases their participation in societal decision-making process. The evaluations of conditional cash transfer programmes demonstrate that poor households do respond to incentives (Lindert et al, 2006; Molyneux, 2008). But it is equally important that the programme that motivates poor households to demand education and health care must also ensure that the schools and hospitals provide quality services that are required for human capital development. A presumption inbuilt in most CCT schemes is that the availability of social services for school education and health care is already in place. Poor health, nutrition, and educational outcomes are the result of both inability to pay for the services and the absence of necessary institutions providing quality services. The direct cash transfers can be particularly beneficial for impoverished households to invest in the education of their daughters provided good quality schooling is available in their neighborhoods. (Sekher and Ram, 2015)

Objectives

The objectives of the study have two facets: a) General objectives and b) Special objectives.

The general objectives of the present study are as follows:

- i) To find out the level of perception of girl students regarding the effectiveness of one-time grant in South 24 Parganas district of West Bengal.
- ii) To assess the attitude of parents regarding the effectiveness of one-time grant in South 24 Parganas district of West Bengal.
- iii) To analyse the role of different field level functionaries responsible for implementation of the scheme, viz. high school teachers, Panchayat members etc. in effective disbursement of one-time grant to the beneficiaries.

The special objectives of the present study are as follows:

- i) To study the present position of the utilization of one-time grant by the girl students.
- ii) To evaluate the role of block level administration in pursuing the effective utilization of Kanyashree one-time grant.
- iii) To suggest an alternative model of utilization of one-time grant.

Methodology

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As per the Kanyashree Dashboard 2023-24, South 24 Parganas has shown the maximum difference in number of Kanyashree applications targeted by the district administration and actual number of applications sanctioned by them. The present study is based on the available secondary analysis of field level data as collected from four Community Development Blocks of West Bengal- which are Bhangar-I, Budgebudge-II, Canning-II and Gosaba. Qualitative analysis of the secondary data has been done for the present study.

Data Analysis

In the present study, we are choosing four community development blocks of South 24 Parganas district of West Bengal. The names of the blocks are Bhangar-I, Budgebudge-II, Canning-II and Gosaba. While studying the correlation analysis between the usefulness of Kanyashree one-time grant in respect of some other important consequential variables.

Table-I: Correlation Analysis Between Usefulness of Kanyashree One-Time Grant in Respect of some other Important Consequential Variables

Table with 5 columns: Consequential Variables, 'r' value for Bhangar-I, 'r' value for Budgebudge-II, 'r' value for Canning-II, 'r' value for Gosaba. Rows include Learning position, How old the respondent is, Profession of guardians, Parents' monthly earning, Earning of family per month, Student's attendance in School or College, and Food supply.

during school/college	significant	significant	significant	significant
Power-supply at home	Highly negative significant	Highly negative significant	Highly negative significant	Highly negative significant
Attainability of Aadhaar card	Highly negative significant	Highly negative significant	Highly negative significant	Non-significant
Distance of the school or college from girl's house	Highly negative significant	Highly negative significant	Highly negative significant	Highly negative significant
Mode of communication to institution	Highly negative significant	Highly significant	Highly significant	Highly negative significant
Convenience of private tuition	Highly negative significant	Highly negative significant	Highly negative significant	Highly negative significant
Efficacy of Kanyashree grant for dropout girls	Highly significant	Highly significant	Highly significant	Non-significant
Family's assent for studying in educational institution	Highly negative significant	Highly negative significant	Non-significant	Highly negative significant
Role of Schools for obtaining Kanyashree grant	Highly significant	Highly significant	Highly significant	Non-significant
Function of Gram Panchayat for receiving Kanyashree grant	Non-significant	Highly significant	Highly significant	Highly significant
Responsibility of Block Development Office for getting	Non-significant	Highly significant	Highly significant	Non-significant

public services				

While studying the same set of consequential variables in four different blocks of South 24 Parganas district of West Bengal, it reveals that out of 17 consequential variables, 8 variables showed their homogeneity characteristics in all four blocks, whereas 9 variables showed their heterogeneity characteristics. In case of Budgebudge-II and Gosaba blocks, since the female literacy rates are lower than other two blocks, hence the role in understanding the learning position is very important. Here, the girl students did not receive any family support in understanding their learning context. In case of Gosaba block, the average age of the respondents was a little bit lower in comparison to other three blocks. As a result, the respondents of Gosaba block were not able to explain the usefulness of Kanyashree one-time grant. In Bhangar-I, Budgebudge-II and Canning-II blocks, a good number of applications had been rejected due to non-availability of Aadhar card of beneficiaries. This justifies the fact that South 24 Parganas has the maximum difference between number of Kanyashree applications targeted by the district administration and number of applications ultimately sanctioned by them. In Bhangar-I and Gosaba blocks, the distance between the beneficiaries' home and the institutions had been quite large enough and the students had poor mode of communication in accessing their institutions. In Bhangar-I, Budgebudge-II and Canning-II blocks, girl students, after receiving one-time grant of Rupees Twenty Five Thousand, dropped out from studies. The reason behind this is that after attaining the age of 18 years, the families got Rupees Twenty Five Thousand from Kanyashree Prakalpa and Rupees Twenty Five Thousand from Ruposhree Prakalpa, which together was utilized for the matrimonial purposes of the dropped out students. One of the objectives of Kanyashree Prakalpa, that is, to resist the early child marriage, is fulfilled. But the other objectives of Kanyashree Prakalpa such as promoting educational attainment for a longer period of time and to financially empower girls could not be achieved. A significant number of parents of Bhangar-I, Budgebudge-II and Gosaba blocks had not shown their interest in promoting the girls' higher education. In comparison to the other three blocks, Gosaba block had lesser number of schools assisting the girl students to avail the benefits of Kanyashree scheme. The panchayat system in Bhangar-I block was not active enough in the implementation of the Kanyashree scheme as compared to the other three blocks. In Bhangar-I and Gosaba blocks, active participation of BDO office in ensuring effective utilization of Kanyashree grant was missing.

Conclusion

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In rural Bengal, the general perception of parents is to marry off their daughters at a younger age. Hence, Kanyashree one-time grant and Ruposhree grant are together giving them the necessary financial support to cover marriage expenses. In most of the places, Kanyashree one-time grant was utilized in purchasing gold jewellery for the matrimonial purposes of the girls and in few cases, the same grant had been utilized in opening their own startup enterprises. In the block level, there is no physical infrastructure through which the block-level administration may arrange a proper need-based training for the girl students so that they can start their own enterprises. The sensitization of parents as well as three-tier panchayat members is very crucial in the successful utilisation of Kanyashree one-time grant. Lack of proper communication between school, panchayat and block-level administration hinders the progress of the scheme to attain its objectives. The proper coordination between school/college level administration, block level administration, Panchayat administration, parental association and beneficiaries would enable successful implementation of Kanyashree one-time grant, which would lead to women empowerment in the district and in the state as a whole.

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